

The Four-Zone, Two-Axis, and Three-Corridor Model for Industrial Development in Ho Chi Minh City

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Abstract:

This study examines the industrial structure of Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC) after its consolidation with Binh Duong and Ba Ria Vung Tau, forming the most integrated interregional economic space in Vietnam. With the combined advantages of the Cai Mep Thi Vai deep sea port, Long Thanh International Airport, and a large industrial logistics ecosystem, the expanded HCMC is positioned to become a major industrial, technological, and logistics hub in Southeast Asia. The assessment of four key industrial sectors reveals constraints in technological capacity, localization, and supply chain linkages. The study proposes a “four zone, two axis” spatial model and an industrial development strategy built on three pillars: total factor productivity (TFP), domestic value added (DVA), and international market access (IMA). Using a weighted average approach based on GRDP structure, the analysis indicates that to achieve a 10 percent annual GRDP growth target, while services and other sectors grow around 7 percent, key industries (33 percent of GRDP) must expand industrial output by approximately 16.1 percent per year. The findings highlight the central role of key industries in regional growth and affirm that reorganizing spatial development along an interregional linkage model based on DVATFPIMA is essential for enhancing the competitiveness of the expanded HCMC during 2025 to 2035. Keywords: key industries; supply chains; industrial corridors; technological innovation; supporting industries

1. Introduction

The consolidation of Ho Chi Minh City with Binh Duong and Ba Ria Vung Tau has created a high tech industrial logistics megaregion with the largest population scale, infrastructure capacity, and connectivity in Vietnam. This new configuration opens a new development space for the Southeast region. In the context of global supply chain competition shifting

from cost advantages to institutional quality, infrastructure, and innovation, this integrated structure strengthens the regions position within the industrial network of Southeast Asia. Achieving double digit GRDP growth is only feasible if key industries play the central role, as they generate the highest value added and create the strongest technological spillovers. Quantifying the required industrial growth rate, based on the share of industry and the performance of other sectors, is essential for designing effective and evidence based industrial policies.

With key industries accounting for roughly thirty five to forty percent of GRDP, such quantification helps determine the appropriate scale of investment, the rate of production expansion, technological requirements, and resource allocation across industrial corridors and functional zones. This transforms the double digit growth target from a slogan into one supported by clear and measurable foundations.

Accordingly, this paper presents four main components: first, an assessment of the current conditions and bottlenecks of key industrial sectors; second, an analysis of the advantages gained from consolidation, with emphasis on the integration of the Cai Mep Thi Vai deep sea port, Long Thanh International Airport, and the industrial logistics network; third, a spatial development plan and industrial corridors designed to optimize value chains; and fourth, a development strategy based on total factor productivity TFP, domestic value added DVA, and international market access IMA, which together enhance productivity and global integration. This framework positions key industries as the primary engine for enabling Ho Chi Minh City to achieve double digit growth during 2025 to 2030.

2. Current Status of Key Industrial Sectors in Ho Chi Minh City

2.1 Overview

The expanded Ho Chi Minh City currently possesses the largest industrial, services, and logistics base in Vietnam, with a GRDP of 115 billion USD in 2024, accounting for 23.5 percent of the national GDP. The region has attracted a cumulative 140 billion USD in FDI and recorded 86 billion USD in export turnover, reflecting its deep integration into regional and global value chains.

Industrial value added from manufacturing accounts for 27 percent of the national total, reaffirming the regions leading role but also indicating pressure to sustain long term growth. Industrial and logistics infrastructure is highly developed, with more than 70 industrial parks, the Cai Mep Thi Vai deep sea port capable of receiving 200,000 DWT vessels, and the Tan Son Nhat Long Thanh aviation network that significantly enhances international market access.

The region has more than 8 million workers and 90 universities, creating a strong base for high tech industries, although the quality of technical labor remains insufficient for smart manufacturing. Intra regional supply chain linkages are extensive but lack depth, and interprovincial coordination mechanisms are not yet strong enough to maximize the efficiency of the industrial and logistics ecosystem.

Overall, the expanded Ho Chi Minh City meets the necessary conditions to become an industrial and logistics megaregion in Vietnam and Southeast Asia. However, to shift from a large region to a leading region, a focused industrial development strategy is required, aligned with the goal of achieving double digit GRDP growth based on TFP, DVA, and IMA for the period 2026 to 2035.

Table 1. Industrial Development Indicators of the Expanded Ho Chi Minh City (2024)

Category	Indicator	Value (2024)	Note
Scale and contribution	GRDP	115 billion USD	23.5 percent of national GDP
	Cumulative FDI	140 billion USD	
	Export turnover	86 billion USD	22 percent of national exports
Manufacturing	Industrial value added	40 billion USD	27 percent of national industrial value added
Industrial and logistics infrastructure	Industrial parks	70 IPs	
	Deep sea port	Ships above 200,000 DWT	Cai Mep Thi Vai

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	Airports	International airports	Tan Son Nhat, Long Thanh
	Road infrastructure	Regional expressways	Connect Southeast, Southwest, Central Highlands
Human resources	Workforce	8 million workers	14 percent of national labor force
	Higher education institutions	90 universities	Excluding colleges and vocational schools
Industrial value chain linkage	Key sectors	Textiles, footwear, machinery, chemicals, electronics	Multi sector supplier networks
Business environment	Overall ranking	Among the top in Vietnam	Competitiveness and FDI attractiveness

Source: Authors synthesis from official data sources.

The economic and industrial scale of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City has grown rapidly over the past decade, as reflected by continued increases in GRDP and industrial value added. This trend reaffirms the regions central role while also showing a shift in the growth structure as traditional industrial drivers weaken, necessitating a new interregional development model.

The combined GRDP of the three provinces increased from under one quadrillion VND in 2010 to nearly three quadrillion VND in 2024, but with notable changes in contribution patterns. Ho Chi Minh City remains the largest contributor, though its growth has slowed due to rapid servicification. Binh Duong has emerged as the primary industrial center due to industrial park expansion and stable FDI inflows, while Ba Ria Vung Tau fluctuates strongly with the downturn of the oil and gas sector.

Industrial value added shows a clear pattern of divergence: Ho Chi Minh City has remained almost flat for an extended period, Binh Duong has grown rapidly and become the main driver of regional industrial expansion, while Ba Ria Vung Tau has declined in line with the oil and gas cycle and has only experienced limited recovery. The share of industrial value added contributed by Ho Chi Minh City to the national total has fallen sharply from more than 50 percent to roughly 25 to 30 percent, indicating a weakening of industrial advantages in the Southern Key Economic Region. In contrast, northern provinces such as Bac Ninh, Bac Giang, Thai Nguyen, and Hai Phong have risen strongly thanks to high tech FDI driven production chains. These shifts highlight the urgent need to restructure industrial space and establish new growth drivers for the expanded Ho Chi Minh City.

Figure 3. Industrial Output of Ho Chi Minh City Compared with the National Total
Source: Authors calculations based on data from the General Statistics Office of Vietnam, 2010–2025.

These trends have generated a cycle of relative decline: industrial growth in Ho Chi Minh City has slowed, Ba Ria Vung Tau has lost its oil and gas pillar, and although Binh Duong has grown rapidly, its expansion is insufficient to offset the slowdown of the entire region. Meanwhile, northern industrial hubs have risen strongly. This situation requires the expanded Ho Chi Minh City to restructure its growth model along an interregional approach, leveraging consolidation to form industrial, logistics, and high tech corridors capable of competing internationally. To achieve the target of double digit GRDP growth, the role of key industries must be clearly quantified, including the necessary increases in industrial output and value added that will enable them to serve as the principal drivers of regional growth.

2.2 Estimating the Required Growth Rate of Industrial Output to Achieve a GRDP Growth Target of 10 Percent

In principle, the GRDP growth rate of Ho Chi Minh City is the aggregated result of its sectoral components, calculated as a weighted average based on each sectors contribution to total GRDP. Assume that the GRDP of the expanded HCMC is divided into two parts:

(i) the key industrial sectors with output Y_k ; and (ii) the remaining sectors (services, construction, agriculture, and others) with output Y_o . Total GRDP is therefore:

$$Y = Y_k + Y_o$$

Let g be the target GRDP growth rate, g_k the growth rate of key industrial sectors, and g_o the growth rate of the remaining sectors. Then:

$$g = s_k \cdot g_k + s_o \cdot g_o$$

where $s_k = Y_k/Y$ is the share of key industries in GRDP, and $s_o = 1 - s_k$ is the share of the remaining sectors. From this expression, the required growth rate of key industrial sectors can be derived as:

$$g_k = \frac{g - s_o \cdot g_o}{s_k}$$

The estimated industrial growth requirement depends on three parameters: the target GRDP growth rate (g), the share of industrial output in GRDP (s_k), and the growth rate of the remaining sectors (g_o). These assumptions make it possible to approximate the industrial output growth range needed to ensure the overall GRDP target is achieved.

Table 2. Estimated industrial output growth rates under different assumptions regarding GRDP contribution shares and the growth performance of the remaining sectors.

		Share of industrial output in GRDP (s_k)									
		25%	27%	29%	31%	33%	35%	37%	39%	41%	43%
Growth rate of non industrial sectors (g_o)	3%	31,0%	28,9%	27,1%	25,6%	24,2%	23,0%	21,9%	20,9%	20,1%	19,3%
	4%	28,0%	26,2%	24,7%	23,4%	22,2%	21,1%	20,2%	19,4%	18,6%	18,0%
	5%	25,0%	23,5%	22,2%	21,1%	20,2%	19,3%	18,5%	17,8%	17,2%	16,6%
	6%	22,0%	20,8%	19,8%	18,9%	18,1%	17,4%	16,8%	16,3%	15,8%	15,3%
	7%	19,0%	18,1%	17,3%	16,7%	16,1%	15,6%	15,1%	14,7%	14,3%	14,0%
	8%	16,0%	15,4%	14,9%	14,5%	14,1%	13,7%	13,4%	13,1%	12,9%	12,7%
	9%	13,0%	12,7%	12,4%	12,2%	12,0%	11,9%	11,7%	11,6%	11,4%	11,3%
	10%	10,0%	10,0%	10,0%	10,0%	10,0%	10,0%	10,0%	10,0%	10,0%	10,0%
	11%	7,0%	7,3%	7,6%	7,8%	8,0%	8,1%	8,3%	8,4%	8,6%	8,7%
	12%	4,0%	4,6%	5,1%	5,5%	5,9%	6,3%	6,6%	6,9%	7,1%	7,3%

13%	1,0%	1,9%	2,7%	3,3%	3,9%	4,4%	4,9%	5,3%	5,7%	6,0%
14%	-2,0%	-0,8%	0,2%	1,1%	1,9%	2,6%	3,2%	3,7%	4,2%	4,7%
15%	-5,0%	-3,5%	-2,2%	-1,1%	-0,2%	0,7%	1,5%	2,2%	2,8%	3,4%
16%	-8,0%	-6,2%	-4,7%	-3,4%	-2,2%	-1,1%	-0,2%	0,6%	1,4%	2,0%

Source: Authors calculations.

With the assumption that key industrial sectors account for 33 percent of GRDP, while the remaining sectors account for 67 percent and grow at around 7 percent annually, the calculations show that industrial output must increase by 16.1 percent per year. This implies that to make the 10 percent GRDP growth target feasible, the key industrial sectors of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City must sustain an annual growth rate significantly higher than the overall economy. This provides an essential quantitative foundation for designing infrastructure, institutional, and enterprise support policies for the period 2025 to 2035.

2.3 Current Status of the Four Key Industrial Sectors in Ho Chi Minh City

The current structure of the key industrial sectors in the expanded Ho Chi Minh City presents a picture of being “strong but insufficient”: large in scale and diverse, yet limited in technological depth, supply chain integration, and production autonomy. This explains why, despite being the industrial center of southern Vietnam, the regions share of national industrial output has gradually declined.

Machinery manufacturing and supporting industries

Ho Chi Minh City and Binh Duong remain the largest hubs in the country, with more than thirty industrial parks and thousands of firms involved in machinery, components, and mold making. However, the sector lacks leading firms, has low localization rates, fragmented supply chains, and does not yet have integrated supporting industry clusters. These issues stem from low R and D investment, limited testing and standardization centers, and the absence of structured procurement mechanisms between FDI firms and domestic suppliers.

Electronics, information technology, and high tech industries

Thu Duc City is emerging as a center for smart devices and chips, while Binh Duong attracts substantial FDI in electronic components. Yet domestic firms remain largely

subcontractors, with DVA of only 15 to 20 percent, and no tier one suppliers meeting international standards. The R and D ecosystem is incomplete, and there are no specialized industrial zones for semiconductors, robotics, or sensors.

Chemicals, pharmaceuticals, energy, and advanced materials

The Phu My – Long Son – Cai Mep cluster plays the core role in national petrochemicals, while Ho Chi Minh City hosts research capabilities in biomedicine and medical equipment. However, supply chain linkages from petrochemicals to pharmaceuticals and medical devices are weak, heavily dependent on imported raw materials, and lack national level testing and certification centers.

Food processing and cold chain logistics

Ho Chi Minh City benefits from a large consumer market and serves as a major distribution gateway, while Cai Mep – Thi Vai supports agricultural and seafood exports, and Binh Duong provides cold storage and logistics. However, the share of firms meeting export standards remains modest, cold chain infrastructure is fragmented, and the region lacks internationally competitive food technology brands.

Overall, the key industrial sectors of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City have large scale, wide market reach, and strong FDI attraction, but remain weak in core technology, R and D, localization, and regional integration. These structural bottlenecks require a new industrial development model based on integrated spatial planning, specialized industrial corridors, and a value chain upgrading strategy focused on increasing DVA, improving TFP, and expanding IMA.

3. Core Advantages of Ho Chi Minh City After Consolidation

After consolidation, the most distinctive and non replicable advantage of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City is its ability to integrate a deep sea port, an international airport, and a large scale industrial logistics ecosystem within a single continuous space. Cai Mep Thi Vai is among the fastest growing deep sea ports in the world and can receive vessels of two hundred thousand DWT sailing directly to Europe and the United States, significantly reducing export costs. Long Thanh International Airport, with a designed cargo capacity

of five million tons annually, will serve as a major hub for high tech and pharmaceutical logistics, while linking directly with high tech parks in Ho Chi Minh City and Binh Duong to form a high efficiency production transport export triangle.

More than thirty modern industrial parks and dense domestic logistics networks across Binh Duong and Ho Chi Minh City create the countrys strongest logistics backbone. The seamless connection between production zones, dry ports, the deep sea port, and the international airport makes the expanded Ho Chi Minh City the only region in Vietnam that fully meets the requirements of international market access (IMA) within a single integrated space – a capacity unmatched by Hai Phong, Hanoi, Da Nang, or Can Tho.

This integrated capability not only lowers costs and accelerates the flow of goods but also enables the formation of a regional scale industrial logistics high tech corridor, allowing the expanded Ho Chi Minh City to reposition itself at a higher level in global supply chains. This represents a core, long term, and decisive advantage for regional competitiveness in the next phase of development.

4. The Four Zone, Two Axis, and Three Corridor Model for Industrial Development in Ho Chi Minh City

4.1 The “Four Zone, Two Axis Linkage” Model

The four zone, two axis linkage model defines the new spatial development structure of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City. It is based on functional specialization, levels of industrial concentration, infrastructure capacity, and the regions ability to participate in global value chains. The four zones operate as an integrated ecosystem, with each zone responsible for a critical stage of the value chain from research and development, to production, logistics, and international services.

Zone One (Thu Duc, Di An, Thuan An) is the high tech and innovation hub, concentrating activities in chip design, artificial intelligence, robotics, biotechnology, big data, and deep tech enterprises. This zone serves as the technological brain of the entire region.

Zone Two (Binh Duong, Cu Chi, Northwest Ho Chi Minh City) is the supporting industry and smart manufacturing area, specializing in precision engineering, components,

materials, and green standard automated factories. It functions as the green manufacturing base supplying inputs for high tech industries.

Zone Three (Ba Ria Vung Tau) acts as Vietnam’s center for seaports, energy, and petrochemicals, hosting the Cai Mep Thi Vai deep sea port cluster, petrochemical complexes, and LNG and green hydrogen projects. This zone is the international gateway connecting directly with global supply chains.

Zone Four (District One, Thu Thiem, South Saigon) is the urban financial and international services center, hosting finance, banking, trade, high tech services, and MICE activities. It serves as the international interface and service backbone for enterprises across the region.

This division creates a deeply integrated ecosystem in which Zone One generates knowledge, Zone Two produces goods, Zone Three supplies energy and logistics, and Zone Four delivers finance and global services. With a structure that is both specialized and interconnected, the expanded Ho Chi Minh City is positioned to elevate its competitiveness within regional and global value chains.

Table 3. The Four Zone, Two Axis Linkage Model

Component	Geographic Area	Core Function	Key Sectors	Linkage Role
Zone 1 High Tech	Thu Duc, Di An, Thuan An	R and D, innovation	Chips, AI, robotics, biotechnology, data centers	Provides knowledge and technology for the entire region
Zone 2 Supporting Industries	Binh Duong, Cu Chi, Northwest HCMC	Smart manufacturing, components, materials	Machinery, components, new materials	Green manufacturing base, increases DVA
Zone 3 Ports and Energy	Ba Ria Vung Tau	Deep sea ports, energy, petrochemicals	LNG, green hydrogen, petrochemicals, maritime logistics	International gateway for trade and energy

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Zone 4 Urban Finance	District One, Thu Thiem, South Saigon	Finance, trade, international services	Finance, MICE, high end services	Provides capital and services for the entire ecosystem
Axis 1	Thu Duc – Binh Duong – Cu Chi	Technology and production	High tech and supporting industries	Increases TFP and DVA
Axis 2	Thu Duc – Long Thanh – Ba Ria Vung Tau	Ports, airport, energy	International logistics	Increases IMA, reduces logistics costs
Integrated Ecosystem	Entire expanded HCMC	Connectivity of knowledge, production, logistics, finance	High tech, manufacturing, exports, finance	Creates an unreplicable competitive advantage

Source: Authors proposal.

4.2 Two Strategic Axes

Within the new spatial structure of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City, the North–South and East–West development axes function as the “backbone framework.” They are not merely transportation routes but strategic economic, technological, and logistics corridors that determine the direction of industrial expansion and the regions capacity to participate in global value chains.

The North–South Axis, stretching from Binh Duong through Ho Chi Minh City to the Cai Mep Thi Vai port cluster, is Vietnams most important industrial and logistics corridor. It concentrates all stages of the value chain: research and development and high tech activities, major production centers, dry port logistics, business services, and direct export gateways to Europe and the United States. This axis forms the principal “flow of goods” in southern Vietnam, reducing export costs and processing time thanks to the deep sea capacity of Cai Mep, while serving as a hub for capital flows, financial services, and high quality human resources.

The East–West Axis connects Long Thanh International Airport, the Thu Duc high tech center, the supporting industry zones of Binh Duong, and the border logistics corridor from Cu Chi to Tay Ninh. It complements the North–South Axis by enabling value chains that rely on air cargo for high tech goods, pharmaceuticals, and high value components. Long Thanh serves as the international gateway; Thu Duc provides knowledge and technology; Binh Duong supports smart manufacturing; and Cu Chi and Tay Ninh link the region to ASEAN trade routes.

The East–West Axis expands the industrial space of Ho Chi Minh City in a more balanced manner, reducing pressure on the urban core and forming a “production–logistics arc” stretching from the airport to the border.

Together, the two axes constitute the “spatial backbone” of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City, ensuring connectivity across three essential elements: (i) knowledge and technology from Thu Duc, Di An, and Thuan An; (ii) supporting industry production from Binh Duong, Cu Chi, and Northwest Ho Chi Minh City; (iii) logistics, seaports, airports, and border trade from Long Thanh and Ba Ria Vung Tau. This integrated configuration creates a multidimensional ecosystem that optimizes the flow of technology, goods, and capital, thereby enhancing competitiveness nationally and internationally.

Table4. The Two Strategic Development Axes of the Expanded Ho Chi Minh City

Strategic Axis	Geographic Area and Connection	Core Economic Function	Key Sectors	Strategic Significance
North–South Axis	Binh Duong – Ho Chi Minh City – Cai Mep	Industrial, logistics, and seaport corridor	Manufacturing, logistics, exports, supporting industries	Creates Vietnams largest goods corridor; links production to export gateways; reduces logistics costs; strengthens global competitiveness

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East–West Axis	Long Thanh – Thu Duc – Binh Duong – Cu Chi – Tay Ninh	Airport, high tech, production, and border logistics corridor	Air cargo, components, pharmaceuticals, high tech industries, cross border logistics	Opens new industrial space; links the airport to high tech value chains; strengthens ASEAN connectivity; expands export markets
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Source: Authors proposal.

In the development model of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City, the interregional ecosystem serves as the foundation connecting technology, goods, human resources, and capital across the four functional zones. This integrated economic and institutional structure creates synergies beyond the capacity of any single locality. A unified data platform enables shared planning, logistics, and labor information, improving decision making. A common labor market allows skilled technical workers to move flexibly between research, production, port operations, and services.

The internal supply chain links industrial parks, ports, and airports, shortening transportation time, reducing costs, and increasing domestic value added (DVA). A unified incentive framework creates a consistent investment environment for high tech industries, semiconductors, pharmaceuticals, and green energy. The interregional ecosystem requires shared R and D centers and harmonized green standards to enhance innovation efficiency and total factor productivity (TFP). Together, these elements enable the expanded Ho Chi Minh City to operate as a unified economic entity with the foundations necessary for achieving sustained double digit growth.

4.3 Industrial Corridors

Within the new development structure of the expanded Ho Chi Minh City, three strategic industrial corridors are established to reorganize production, logistics, and technology space toward specialization and regional integration. These corridors function as the

backbone linking technology hubs, manufacturing centers, and energy nodes to deep sea ports and international airports.

The Southeast Seaport Industrial Corridor, stretching from Binh Duong through Ho Chi Minh City to Cai Mep Thi Vai, is the most important production and export axis. It specializes in machinery, electronics, materials, supporting industries, and food processing; it also hosts the countrys largest cold chain capacity and the strongest international market access (IMA).

The Long Thanh Airport High Tech Corridor, connecting Thu Duc and Di An with Long Thanh, serves as the primary air cargo hub for high tech exports including semiconductors, robotics, precision electronics, pharmaceuticals, and components. With substantial cargo capacity, Long Thanh is expected to become a strategic transshipment point of Southeast Asia.

The Energy – Petrochemical – Advanced Materials Corridor, linking Phu My and Long Son to Binh Duong, supplies foundational inputs for the entire region, including petrochemicals, LNG, green hydrogen, and advanced polymer materials. This enhances material autonomy and raises domestic value added (DVA).

Together, the three corridors form the spatial framework for industrial, logistics, and high tech development in the expanded Ho Chi Minh City. They ensure full integration between research, production, energy, and logistics, thereby enhancing the regions competitiveness and growth momentum.

5. Strategies to Leverage Advantages for the Development of Key Industries

The expanded Ho Chi Minh City must develop shared research centers, testing facilities, and unified standards, while establishing a regional Innovation Fund of ten thousand to twenty thousand billion VND to support automation and green manufacturing. Programs applying AI, IoT, robotics, MES, and ERP must be implemented across the region to diffuse technology from Thu Duc to industrial and energy zones.

To enhance DVA, the region needs to cultivate a cohort of around one hundred core enterprises capable of becoming tier one suppliers in high tech industries. Structured

procurement mechanisms between FDI firms and domestic firms must be institutionalized. Strengthening linkages between supporting industry clusters in Binh Duong and North Saigon with the Thu Duc high tech zone and Northwest manufacturing centers will create a closed, self sustaining regional supply chain and reduce import dependence.

To increase IMA, Long Thanh, Thu Duc, and Cai Mep must evolve into a super trade corridor for high tech goods, components, pharmaceuticals, and processed agricultural products. A regional one stop logistics mechanism could reduce clearance time and handling costs by about thirty percent. A unified export tax incentive package for goods moving through Long Thanh, Cat Lai, and Cai Mep would attract global production chains. A strong interregional governance mechanism is also essential. The establishment of a Regional Industrial and Logistics Spatial Coordination Committee with authority over budgets, incentives, industrial land planning, and green standards would replace fragmented development with a coherent, interconnected system aligned with the needs of high quality FDI and frontier technologies.

Strategic human resources remain a decisive factor. The region needs a coordinated training network involving Vietnam National University Ho Chi Minh City, Eastern International University, and Ba Ria Vung Tau University to train engineers in semiconductors, robotics, energy, and advanced materials. High tech training centers in Thu Duc and Binh Duong will supply skilled technicians and form an interregional labor market supporting large scale production.

6. Conclusion

The expanded Ho Chi Minh City possesses a unique national advantage: the convergence of a deep sea port, an international airport, and a large scale industrial logistics ecosystem within a single integrated space. This foundation enables the region to move toward a development trajectory based on global connectivity. When reorganized through modern spatial planning, the three interregional industrial corridors combined with a DVA–TFP–IMA based strategy will establish a megaregion of industry, technology, and logistics with competitiveness on par with Bangkok, Kuala Lumpur, or Jakarta.

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The three pillars of IMA, TFP, and DVA provide the momentum to enhance both the scale and quality of growth. Coupled with a strong regional coordination institution and high quality human resources, the expanded Ho Chi Minh City is positioned to become Vietnam's leading center for industry, high tech development, and logistics, and a major hub for ASEAN. With this structure, the region not only serves as the locomotive for southern Vietnam but also contributes decisively to the national goal of becoming a modern, high income industrialized country by 2045.

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